

A Report about:

Study leadership approaches, change management theories, and human resource management practices during Corvid-19: A study of how leaders can mitigate negative effects of change.

SUAAD SAID ABDULLAH

Abstract

Purpose: This report discusses how different conceptual approaches and change management theories can be implemented while dealing with Covid situations and the role of leaders and Human resource management in managing the change by implementing flexible leadership approaches. Also, classify employees according to how they perceive the change.

Methodology: This report discusses Menninger's model, the Elisabeth Kübler-Ross model, Lewin's change management model, HRM approaches, transactional leadership, and transformational leadership. Information is collected from ProQuest resources.

Result: The report concludes that most change management theories are closely related, but leadership approaches are applied differently in each phase. Taking employees from unfreeze to refreeze requires a considerable amount of effort. In the first stage, transactional leadership is more critical since the leader needs to make the decision even if the plan is imperfect. Employees need to feel that the situation is under control. The leader should focus on destructive employees, since they are feeling fear and confusion, and they should trust the leader to move forward. Phase two focuses more on negotiation and problem-solving. Therefore, leaders devise a plan for how to implement the changes. This phase is more about transformational leadership than transactional leadership. During phase three, employees will engage, accept, and move on; therefore, transformational leadership will result in the highest level of employee satisfaction. Additionally, HR must leverage virtual employee models and transformative e-HRM through the use of AI-based tools and approaches." According to the report, HR, change management models, and leadership models should align with equity and diversity concerns.

Keywords: Human Resource Management, change management theories, transactional leadership, and transformational leadership, Constructive and Destructive employees.

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Introduction

Life is a constant state of change. The cycle of growth and decay is as essential to our existence as the need for water and air_(Anderson & Anderson, 2010) Corvid 19 is one of the pandemic crises that touches many aspects: Social, Economic, Political, Organizational and Human aspects. The government roles to confine, work virtually, and de-confine severely impact organizations strategy and human resource management approach. Venkatesh_(2008) summarized that creating and maintaining a healthy and productive work culture is a significant responsibility of Human Resources. Staffing, superannuation, and other employee-related activities are all handled by human resources. Consequently, Human Resources contributes to achieving organizational objectives through improved productivity, reducing costs, generating internal resources and profits, and better customer service. Therefore, this report will discuss the changes in Human Resource Management and the recommendations to overcome these changes. For an organization, corvid represents a change, and for a leader, it means a change. Whenever a change is introduced, many people will experience an emotional reaction. A commitment begins with initial resistance, moves through letting go, and ends with promise_(Anderson & Anderson, 2010), so A leader's role is to be the voice of an organization's unified metanarrative that embodies a vision of an inclusive culture_(Ferdman, et al., 2013) Thus, this report will aim to discuss change management theories and leadership aspects as tools to convey the change. According to Jones and Recardo_(2013, p. 5), "Change management is a product of multiple disciplines and practices that have emerged in response to business change needs throughout the modern business era". Burns (1978 cited in_(Dugan, 2017, p. 183)) defined transactional leadership as the process of "inducing followers to act for certain goals that represent the values

and the motivations— the wants and needs, the aspirations and expectations— of both leaders and followers". Also, Burns believed transforming leadership developed "a relationship of mutual stimulation and elevation that converts followers into leaders and may convert leaders into moral agents ... the type of leadership that can produce social change."

This moment of truth that leaders should be most concerned with, regardless of the model they use. Through this shift, commitment and transformation are possible. Otherwise, people remain stuck in resistance. So what is the best way to encourage this transformation? ([Anderson & Anderson, 2010](#)).

Methodology

The report's methodology involves a review of different kinds of literature using ProQuest resources (e-book & e-journals). The report focused on Quantitative research, and secondary sources had been used.

Report Implications:

The report lacked qualitative and primary sources which can touch the discussed topic directly.

Discussion

1.0 The Change Management theories implemented during Corvid-19:

1. Elisabeth Kübler-Ross Model: Denial → Anger → Bargaining → Depression → Acceptance [_\(Anderson & Anderson, 2010\).](#)
2. Lewin's change management model: Unfreeze → Change → Refreeze [_\(Lewin, 1958\).](#)
3. Menninger's model [\(See Figure 1\)](#) [_\(Elrod & Tippett, 2002\).](#)

Schneider and Goldwasser (1998, as cited in [K \(Elrod & Tippett, 2002\)](#)) outlined the role of management in understanding and leading organizations through change. They used Menninger's model to illustrate the impact of change on organizational performance [\(See Figure 1\)](#).

[Figure 1 International Association of Machinists' change model](#)

A change is announced: When the government announced about the corvids and the need to confine everyone. Therefore, confinement is a form of supervision for employees and people in general that have the below impacts on employees:

1. Shock: Confusion

People do not understand what is happening because the whole situation is new and shocking to them. Consequently, people's natural reaction is to stand still, observe it, and wait for further developments.

2. Denial Period (Resistance): During the period of denial, they ignore the facts, believing that it will pass quickly and do not need to overthink it. This stage is called Denial in Elisabeth Kübler-Ross Model [\(Anderson & Anderson, 2010\)](#).

3. Bargaining: Negotiations will ensue on what should be done to minimize the impact.

For instance, previously working hours were 40 hours. The employee negotiated that for 30 hours since everything moved virtual, and many meetings that were previously held physically or on the field are no longer necessary. This stage is called Anger in Elisabeth Kübler-Ross Model [\(Anderson & Anderson, 2010\)](#).

4. Greif: Frustration, a sense of loss. When the employee realizes that he or she will face this situation for months, or even years, and must accept changes. This stage is called Depression in Elisabeth Kübler-Ross Model [\(Anderson & Anderson, 2010\)](#).

*These four-phase steps is called Unfreezing stage in Lewin's change management model [\(Lewin, 1958\)](#).

5. Acceptance: When the employee decides to give a trial. This stage is called Acceptance in Elisabeth Kübler-Ross Model [\(Anderson & Anderson, 2010\)](#).
6. Exploration: Integration of the new reality.
7. Opportunity: Develop new ideas and approaches. Example,
8. Accomplishment: Agree to implement the new concept.

*These four-phase steps is called the change stage in Lewin's change management model [\(Lewin, 1958\)](#).

9. Creativity: Positive perception of the change by adopting the new idea. Consequently, it becomes the new environment or the new stability in their lives.

* These phase steps are called refreezing stage in Lewin's change management model [\(Lewin, 1958\)](#).

It is essential to accompany employees throughout the process so that it does not take too long.

As a result of the process taking too long, the engagement part never happens when another change occurs, like when the confinement period ends. Then, another period of change within

the organization happens, with new projects and modifications. If a confinement change is not completely implemented within an organization, the employees are unhappy because they were confirmed without engaging the last change. Therefore, it is getting complex as the employees are not aboard on plans to get together.

2.0 Organic Change and Human System- Dynamics:

Division of employees when the new change happens and in this case with Corvid-19 called people dynamic [\(Anderson & Anderson, 2010\)](#):

1. Constructive: they are getting on board quickly, making sure everything is going smoothly. Nevertheless, you will have employees who are more destructive by nature. Some employees are more passive or active when it comes to change. Most of the leaders within the constructive side will try to bring as many employees as possible to this site since this is where people put their energy to move into a new environment.
2. Destructive: In reality, this is not what happened. Many employees will be classified as resistant and will feel fear, anxiety, and a sense of vulnerability. This will cause them to procrastinate or withdraw.

3.0 Tools-influenced changing:

What are the tools at your disposal as a leader to deal with this situation?

1. Transactional leadership
2. Transformational leadership

I. Transactional leadership: Essentially, this type of leadership depends on the reciprocal and

deterministic relationship between a leader and his or her subordinates. To motivate subordinates, leaders engage in bargaining with them. Leaders use their relative positional power to control the bargaining process to issue and receive benefits for continuing positive behaviour. There are multiple characteristics of transactional leadership. A transactional leader uses contingent rewards (e.g., work for pay or time off) to support explicit or implicit agreement on the goals to achieve the desired rewards. [\(Vito, et al., 2014\)](#) In Corvid-19, transnational leadership is needed because critical decisions must be made. Also, in emergency situations. Additionally, employees who are not experts in their field may face challenging situations.

II. Transformational leadership: Like the transactional leadership theory, the transformational leadership theory includes power and influence in the leadership process. According to Vito et al. [\(2014\)](#), the relationship between a leader and a subordinate is based on emotion.

Transformative leaders use four characteristics to motivate behaviour: charisma, inspiration, individual consideration, and intellectual stimulation.

4.0 Fixable Leadership approach and leader Role:

Adapted from Yurl and Lepsinger (2004), the Fixable Leadership approach that the leader must follow:

I. Phase 1: During phase 1, people are still in denial that the change is occurring. Hence, it's an emotional reaction that puts people into a situation where they think they want some time to analyze what's happening. If we take the example of phase 1, where people are stunned by the fact that there has been a major shift when they are confined, then the same effect will occur with the de-confinement phase.

❖ Here are the actions the leader needs to take:

1. Take control of the situation: The leader should analyze the case, for example,

the confining and de-confining, and assess its impacts on the following areas summarised by Anderson & Anderson (2010) See [\(See Figure 2\)](#)

- a. Organizational dimension: The law and regulations must be followed during confining and de-confining. Also, regarding productivity and quality, how can focus customer satisfaction without physical interaction.
- b. People dimension: For example, some employees during the de-confining might be absent because of their fear of getting the virus.
- c. Process: For instance, implementing a virtual desktop so the IT team can help track data and system security.

A good analysis will create a clear action plan that the leader will take to reality. The stage requires focusing more on transactional leadership since the leader needs to oversee taking the decision even the plan is not perfect. The critical part is the employees perceive that you do have the situation under control. The leader should focus on destructive employees (resistance) since they are under fear and confusion, and they should trust the leader to move on.

[Figure 2. Three Critical Focus Areas of Change Leadership.](#) (Anderson & Anderson, 2010, p. 25)

2. Communication: Leaders should transparently communicate the plan's outline.
3. Implementation: To overcome resistance to change, change management specialists usually share more information and involve people more in implementation (Anderson & Anderson, 2010). Therefore, employees must feel that they are part of the solution by implementing decisions and providing them with timely direction.

II.Phase 2: This phase focuses more on negotiation and problem-solving. As a result, leaders assemble a plan to see how these changes will be implemented in practice.

❖ The leader must take the following actions:

1. Long-term plan (Strategic planning): Since the shock phase is over, it is important at this

phase that the leader should have a long-term vision or plan and go into the details and get feedback from the employees. The plan must be clear to everybody. For instance, the long-term goal is to communicate with the customers from a distance. Therefore, in this phase, the leader should focus more on transformational leadership than transactional. Happy and committed people are more productive; they can learn and adapt more quickly than resistant, defensive, and angry individuals [\(Anderson & Anderson, 2010\)](#).

Therefore, the leader should focus on constructive employees. This phase requires motivation and mobilization of employees, who later bring the other employees from the destructive stage to the constructive phase.

2. Discussion, engagement, and negotiation: Leaders and staff should be trained in personal growth to implement a transformational change strategy and become a more inclusive organization. This is one way that conscious change leadership pays much more attention to human dynamics than change management [\(Anderson & Anderson, 2010\)](#); [\(Ferdman et al., 2013\)](#). Thus, the discussion in this phase requires the employees to be involved in conducting a Covid-19 survey. This will help to understand and have a complete picture of the employees thinking and feeling rather than making a decision based on assumptions.

III. Phase 3: During this phase, people will engage, move forward, and accept the situation; therefore, transformational leadership will generate the highest level of employees satisfaction. Thus, the leader should mainly focus on creating a positive climate and supporting employees by educating and coaching them, so it is easy to carry out the plan. Also, it is crucial to delegate the challenges mandated to employees by taking risks and making the change. This leads the employees to engage by taking responsibility for doing

tasks. In inclusive organizations, shared leadership can develop at all levels, including those without formal leadership positions. Feeling valued and respected increases people's sense of belonging and willingness to go above and beyond expectations [\(Ferdman, et al., 2013\)](#).

5.0 Human Resource Management Approach During the Pandemic.

During the Corvid-19 pandemic, there are visible changes occurred in Human Resource Management process and approaches:

1. Home as the new office. The organizational structure is determined by the organization's strategy, which is determined by its interaction with the business environment [\(Venkatesh, 2008\)](#). For example, Microsoft adopted a hybrid workplace as a new strategy during the pandemic.
2. HR is changing many of its activities, such as recruiting, onboarding, performance management, and firing decisions. Binyamin and Carmeli [\(2010\)](#) defined this as the dynamics and flexibility of HRM processes (the ability to adapt to changes in the organization's task environment, strategic orientation, and core technologies). Also, According to Bissola & Imperatori [\(2019\)](#), when an IT asset (e.g., an information system or data) provides an organizational resource with new or modified capabilities, that resource is more likely to achieve its goals. Therefore, virtual structures are becoming increasingly common to simulate camaraderie and exploration.
3. Creating a virtual employee experience requires HR to redesign the employee journey

and measure the virtual participant experience elements, including work-life balance, well-being, connection, and collaboration. Bissola & Imoeratori [\(2019, p. 22\)](#) define this trend as Transformational e-HRM, which is "the ability of HR to promote Transformational HRM through the exploitation of AI productivity tools and approaches". One example is the increasing use of online conferencing. In addition, zoom can be used to provide job shadowing to new hires.

4. HR and driving force: The Corvid-19 pandemic period has seen a significant shift in business operations. It has also caused significant personal hardship for workers around the world. During all this chaos, HR had been the frontline, facilitating employees' handling of business requirements. Addressing the concerns and questions of employees and focusing on their mental and emotional well-being. [\(Shivarudrappa, et al., 2009\)](#). To success during the pandemic, digital transformation must be accelerated. It appears that HRM design should be contextual, i.e., adaptable to the contingencies in the external and internal environments that have the greatest impact on the HRM characteristics [\(Milikic, 2020\)](#).
5. According to the contingency approach - "best fit," a company must analyze its sector and environment before implementing any strategy [\(Iqbal, 2019\)](#). Most HR transformations today focus on HR self-service departments. The trend is two-fold: first, if the HR department still uses paperwork, it should be digitized; second, if your HR department performs repetitive tasks, it should be automated. In this way, digitalization and automation help HR professionals maximize their efficiency.

6.0 Leadership theories and HR (Business Analytics) are weak in front of diversity and inclusion

Despite the evolution of prominent leadership theories and the increasing incorporation of new social contexts, they tend to ignore equity, diversity, and social justice issues in their conceptualizations. An organization might need to examine the norms and behaviours that characterize its culture and inquire how those practices may hinder women from finding their voices or making the most of their contributions. For example, during de-confining, the employees are supposed to go back to work, but the pregnant woman will be at high risk of getting the virus. Also, Business Analytics (BA) capabilities in HRM are frequently evaluated as "weak" by organizations. Even though many organizations believe HR Analytics is essential for business performance and measuring the effectiveness of leadership approach and change management cycle [\(Bissola & Imperatori, 2019\)](#). Binyamin & Carmeli [\(2010\)](#) described it as uncertainty. "Uncertainty refers to lacking the information needed to achieve a given level of performance, the inability to predict future events, or the implications of a certain action" [\(Binyamin & Carmeli, 2010, p. 1005\)](#)

I.Recommendations:

➤ It is crucial to link diversity and inclusion with company values. Also, Human resource policies such as recruiting, onboarding, succession planning, identification of high potential, leadership development, work-life balance, and accommodation for differently-abled employees, as well as benefits, rewards, and recognition programs, all need to support the goal of inclusion. Most organizations already do so today [\(Ferdman, et al., 2013\)](#).

- There is a need for a system to help HRM drive the business forward during the pandemic. Talent Management Information Technology (TM IT) vendors, such as SAP, often communicate how their products enable organizations to combine talent and technology innovatively and creatively to facilitate new working methods [\(Bissola & Imperatori, 2019\)](#). Also, a software-based point solution can be inquired through regular surveys. This is an important tool for transformational leadership. If that is the case, it can be managed by strategic HR survey management units. For example, PwC's survey of 1,379 CEOs from 79 countries concluded talent and technology are the two primary sources of innovation for organizations worldwide [\(Bissola & Imperatori, 2019\)](#).
- Digital technologies such as collaborative social platforms have changed the way people work and provide organizations with new and varied data sources that can be analyzed to optimize organizational and individual outcomes, especially when these technologies are integrated with traditional ones [\(Bissola & Imperatori, 2019\)](#).

Conclusion:

Among the most significant aspects of this report are (1) it discusses the different conceptual approaches and change management theories and how they can be applied to the Corvid situation, and (2) it discusses the role of leaders and human resource management in managing the change through a flexible leadership approach. Also, employees were categorized according to their perceptions of the changes. Data was gathered from ProQuest databases. According to the report, change management theories are closed to one another; however, leadership approaches are integrated differently depending on the stage. It is

imperative for both the organization and the employees to understand the leadership behind these theories and the implementation process. In dealing with change, leadership theories provide the most valuable guidance for leaders. The majority of the changes relate to internal strategic changes; the Corvid incident had a health-external impact on the organizational strategies and human resource management approaches. In the first phase of refreezing change, the report recommends that the leader should not jump directly into a transformational leadership approach. Furthermore, human resource management faced a number of implications regarding the management and hiring of employees during corvid, and they had to focus on e-HR or digital HR in order to be able to control the process. Still, these theories could not address some other factors, such as pregnant women or people with high infection risks during the period of de-confinement.

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